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Modern Clinical Diagnostic Methods of Physiology and Hygiene of Adolescent Girls

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***Abstract:** This article reviews the causes of infectious and inflammatory diseases of the genitals in children and adolescents and the frequency of occurrence of this pathology. The clinical picture and diagnosis of the main nosological forms of infectious and inflammatory diseases of the genitals are described, and the main treatment regimens for inflammatory diseases of the genitals in children and adolescents are presented.*

***Key words:** vulvitis, vulvovaginitis, salpingitis-salpingo-oophoritis, inflammatory diseases of the genitals*

Introduction: The incidence of gynecological pathology in children, according to the All-Russian Children's Medical Examination in 2002, reaches 15% [3, 14]. Inflammatory diseases of the genital organs in girls include: vulvitis, vulvovaginitis, salpingitis and salpingoophoritis. One of the most common diseases of the reproductive system in girls is inflammatory diseases of the genitals, which account for more than 50% of visits to the gynecologist by parents and adolescent girls [2-4, 6, 1, 2-4, 9, 10].

Considering the structure of reproductive health of girls, according to the data of preventive examinations in Russia in 2009-2010, inflammatory diseases of the external genitalia account for more than 40%, and internal genitalia for an average of 7-8%, ranking third after primary dysmenorrhea [3, 14]. Vulvitis and vulvovaginitis account for 60-70% of gynecological diseases in girls under 8 years of age, which is associated with certain physiological characteristics of the child's body [2, 3, 5, 6, 12, 14, 20].

From the first days after birth, the girl's vagina is populated with opportunistic microorganisms. They play an important role in maintaining the health of the vulva and vagina. A decrease in the reactivity of

the child's body, which often occurs after some illness or in the course of a chronic inflammatory process, leads to an imbalance between the child's body and the vaginal microflora. Therefore, it is not surprising that the appearance of vaginal discharge in a child usually precedes some illness, most often a cold [2-6, 12, 14, 16, 20].

Symptoms of inflammation of the vulva and vagina include redness of the mucous membranes and skin of the external genitalia and vaginal discharge. Girls may experience itching or burning in the external genital area.

The history and gynecological examination data do not always allow to determine the cause of vulvovaginitis. For this purpose, additional research methods are used: microscopy of vaginal smears, microbiological examination, etc. [2-6, 8, 10, 12, 14, 16-20].

The degree of vaginal damage is determined by examining the vagina using vaginoscopy or a lighted vaginal speculum. Patients present with hyperemia (redness) of the vaginal walls, cheesy deposits, and discharge. Vaginoscopy allows for visualization of a foreign body and the removal of material from the posterior vaginal opening or cervical canal for microscopic and other types of examination [1-3, 5, 6, 12, 14, 16, 20]. Vaginal smears of healthy girls aged 5-8 years show a few leukocytes (up to 5 per field of view) and epithelial cells (1-3 per field of view), the flora is sparse, often coccal; Lactobacilli are absent in the vaginal microflora of preschool girls, which appear in puberty. In menstruating girls, the vaginal microflora is more abundant and corresponds to the microflora of women of reproductive age. It should be noted that children do not always experience combined inflammatory processes of the vulva and vagina. Vulvitis is a very common condition, which is characterized by damage to the vaginal opening by microorganisms [2, 3, 5, 6, 14, 16, 20]. Vulvitis is often observed in girls with pathologies of the urinary system, infection from the intestine, infection from the outside, non-compliance with the rules of the medical and hygienic regimen. The inflammatory process in the vagina caused by intestinal flora is provoked by *E. coli* or enterococci. Pinworms are parasites of the large intestine. When examining the genitals, attention is paid to thickening of the anal folds and their hyperemia. The child complains of itching in the anus, abdominal pain (usually in the umbilical region), and loss of appetite.

Research methods and materials: Therapy consists of two stages. This is the treatment of enterobiasis and the treatment of the inflammatory process of the vulva and vagina [2, 3, 5, 6, 20]. For the treatment of enterobiasis, pyrantel and vermoz are prescribed at a rate of 10 mg per 1 kg of the child's body weight. After a month, the treatment should be repeated. Parents should pay attention to hygiene deficiencies, the possibility of the whole family becoming infected with enterobiasis, therefore, it is necessary to recommend treatment to all family members, as well as to strictly observe the daily toileting of the child's external genitalia [2, 3, 6].

Parents come to their daughters with complaints of bloody-purulent discharge in vulvovaginitis due to a foreign body in the vagina. The foreign body is removed by the gynecologist, after which the vagina should be washed with a disinfectant solution. This procedure usually cures the inflammatory process within 2-3 days.

Atopic vulvovaginitis is observed in girls with exudative diathesis and other manifestations of food allergy [2, 3, 6, 11, 12, 14, 16, 20]. Local treatment includes baths with infusions and decoctions of herbal preparations (chamomile, oak bark, calendula), if they are tolerated. It is advisable to use Advantan ointment (0.1% methylprednisolone aceponate). Mycotic vulvovaginitis is caused by fungi of the genus *Candida*, whose

There are more than 100 species. The most common is *Candida albicans*. Patients complain of cheesy discharge, burning and itching in the area of the external genitalia. Treatment is carried out with antimycotics of the polyene series (nystatin, levorin, amphotericin B); imidazole drugs (ketoconazole, miconazole, bifonazole, clotrimazole, canesten); triazole drugs (fluconazole, itraconazole, etc.). These drugs inhibit the synthesis of ergosterol, the main element of the fungal cell membrane, which causes lysis of the cells of the latter.

Bacterial vulvovaginitis can have an acute onset or a sluggish course, with or without periods of exacerbation. With bacterial vulvovaginitis, hyperemia of the vulva, perineal skin, labia, and moderate yellowish vaginal discharge are observed. Elements of pyoderma can be observed on the skin of the groin and around the labia. Areas of hyperemia can be observed on the walls of the vagina.

After vaginoscopy and taking smears, it is recommended to wash the vagina with a weak disinfectant solution (manganese, rivanol, chlorhexidine, etc.) or simply with an isotonic solution of sodium chloride, and insert suppositories with sulfonamides or broad-spectrum antibiotics. Such treatment can be carried out daily until the results of microbiological and immunological studies are obtained. Therapy can have a positive effect even before the final research results are available. At the same time, it is necessary to sanitize chronic foci of infection, treat skin diseases, and carry out antiallergic therapy. After receiving laboratory data, a diagnosis and treatment plan are determined. Vaginal procedures are performed daily for 7-10 days. Then hygienic baths are used [2, 3].

In recent years, the role of sexually transmitted infections (STIs) in the etiology of vulvovaginitis in girls has increased - chlamydia, mycoplasmosis and ureaplasmosis, trichomoniasis, genital herpes, gonorrhea, etc. [2, 3, 6, 14, 19, 20].

Specific vulvovaginitis requires complex treatment with the help of immunobiological drugs and physiotherapy, with the mandatory use of etiotropic therapy aimed at eliminating intestinal and vaginal dysbacteriosis (long-term courses of treatment with several antibiotics to which the specific pathogen is sensitive).

Trichomonas vulvovaginitis affects adolescent girls with sufficient estrogen levels in the blood, since the presence of *trichomonas* requires glycogen, which is produced only in the mature epithelium of the vulva and vagina. Patients are bothered by abundant, frothy, yellowish discharge and itching of the vulva. *Trichomonas* is detected in a local vaginal smear. The disease is sexually transmitted, and infection can occur during childbirth. The household route of infection is suspected, therefore it is necessary to identify possible sources of infection and carry out appropriate treatment, including metronidazole, 1 tablet 4 times a day for 5 consecutive days. Local toileting is carried out with weak disinfectants.

Conclusions: *Chlamydia trachomatis* is distinguished from other pathogens of vulvovaginitis by the presence of an intracellular development cycle. *Chlamydia* is sexually transmitted, so its detection in the vagina of girls most likely indicates infection during childbirth or transmission of infection through the mucous membrane of the eyelids. *Chlamydia* should be sought in girls with persistent vulvovaginitis, conjunctivitis, arthritis, and bronchitis. The clinical picture is characterized by a mild inflammatory process with very poor, scanty or moderate vaginal discharge. Treatment should be comprehensive. This includes therapy with antibiotics and antimicrobial drugs, eubiotics, stimulation of the body's defenses, and maintenance of intestinal microflora.

Not all drugs used for adults can be recommended for the treatment of children. Antibiotics can be prescribed to children: 1) doxycycline 0.1 g 2 times a day for 7 days; 2) erythromycin 2 g / day (for children under 8 years old) 50 mg per 1 kg of the child's body weight per day, divided into 4 doses for 7 days; 3) azithromycin 10 mg per 1 kg of body weight on the 1st day of treatment, then 5 mg per 1 kg of the child's body weight 1 hour before meals for 4 days; 4) methacycline 0.6 g / day for 10 days; 5) ersin 0.4 g 3 times a day for 3 days; 6) josamycin 1 g / day for 10 days. Along with antibiotics, nystatin is prescribed up to 2 million per day.

Additionally, it is necessary to use eubiotics: bifidumbacterin orally in 2 to 5 doses 3 times a day for 2-3 weeks in a row; suppositories with lactobacterin in the vagina. Control of vaginal smears is carried out at the end of treatment and 3 weeks after its completion.

Bacterial vaginosis (gardnerellosis) occurs in 36% of children with vulvovaginitis [2, 3]. Patients complain of liquid milky or grayish leucorrhoea with a putrid fishy odor. No obvious inflammatory reaction of the tissues was observed during examination. The diagnosis is based on the presence of the following factors: homogeneous vaginal discharge; "main" epithelial cells in Gram-stained vaginal smears; a large number of microflora; a predominance of epithelial cells over leukocytes; a positive amine test (the appearance of a putrid fishy odor when mixing equal parts of potassium hydroxide and vaginal discharge). Treatment involves dalacin - a vaginal cream (2% clindamycin phosphate - a broad-spectrum antibiotic that effectively suppresses anaerobic flora) for 5-7 days or metronidazole 500 mg 2 times a day for 7 days. Common genital herpes occurs in waves, recurs every 1-2-6 months. The clinical picture is vivid, characterized by vesicular and erosive-ulcerative rashes on the mucous membrane of the vulva and vagina, on the skin of the labia and perineum. Sometimes hyperemia and swelling of the skin and mucous membranes are observed. Patients are always bothered by burning and pain in the area of the external genitalia. For the treatment of children, zovirax 200 mg 2 times a day for 7 days, xelepin 100 mg 2-3 times a day for 7 days in a row, interferon inducers - alpizarin in 100 mg tablets, bonafton ointment; tavegil, 2 tablets 2 times a day, locally - 30% interferon ointment, oxolinic ointment, 30% megazin ointment, instillation of a solution of poludan into the vagina. Girls also experience another type of viral infection - papillomavirus infection. Although it is believed that the transmission of papillomavirus infection occurs sexually, it occurs in preschool girls. Genital warts are usually located in the perineum and can have a thin stalk or a wide base. Treatment is carried out with drugs that cause necrosis of condylomas. The skin around the condyloma should be lubricated with ointment to protect it from the drug. Apply a 30% alcohol solution of podophyllin, feresol, lubricate the papillomas for 10-60 minutes, repeat the procedures after 2 weeks. Laser therapy, cryo- and electrosurgery with local or general anesthesia are successfully used. In sexually inactive girls, in the prepubertal period, inflammation of the uterine appendages is a casuistic phenomenon [2, 3, 5, 6, 12, 14, 20].

Discussion: In most cases, inflammation of the appendages is secondary, i.e. The infection is transmitted by hematogenous or lymphogenous routes from the organ affected by the inflammatory process to the fallopian tubes and ovaries. The main causes of secondary salpingitis and salpingoophoritis in girls are: acute purulent appendicitis;

inflammatory processes in the small and large intestines; other inflammatory processes of the abdominal organs (cryptogenic peritonitis); chronic foci of infection.

If there is a history of sexual activity, frequent change of sexual partners, infection of the external genital tract (specific and nonspecific colpitis), the infection can be introduced into the small pelvis by the ascending route. Acute salpingitis and salpingoophoritis can develop, which, if untreated and with

a decrease in immunity, can be complicated by tubo-ovarian formations of uterine appendages [3, 6, 7, 10, 14, 19-21].

Clinical signs of inflammatory diseases of the internal genital organs in girls include: variability of pain syndrome, menometrorrhagia as the only sign of a purulent-inflammatory process in the pelvic cavity, and a discrepancy between the clinical picture of the disease and the severity of purulent-inflammatory lesions of the uterus.

Diagnostic criteria for acute salpingo-oophoritis in children: a sharp deterioration in the patient's general condition; the appearance of signs of peritoneal irritation; pain on palpation of the uterine appendages; "low" on palpation of the uterine appendages; vaginal discharge.

Diagnostic criteria for chronic salpingo-oophoritis in children: pain in the lower abdomen for a month or more; pain on palpation of the uterine appendages; pain when trying to move the tubo-tubo-ovarian formations; menstrual disorders.

Ultrasound examination of most patients with inflammation of the appendages helps to make a correct diagnosis. The only exception is chronic oophoritis, which is devoid of specific ultrasound signs. In acute oophoritis, echograms show a significant enlargement of the ovaries. In addition, their shape and size can change to such an extent that they create the impression of a tumor. Further development of the infectious process can lead to the development of pyovarium - purulent dissolution of the ovary. The echographic picture of such a formation resembles one of the variants of the image of a corpus luteum cyst [9].

Inflammatory changes in the joints have a wide range of visual possibilities - from regularly shaped formations with clear internal contours to shapeless, poorly defined conglomerates [9, 15].

Conclusion: On ultrasound, tubo-ovarian abscess is characterized by the presence of an appendiceal mass with a predominance of a cystic component. On transabdominal ultrasound, the contours of the abscess appear blurred, and the ovary is often not clearly visible [15]. Differential diagnosis of tubo-ovarian abscess should be carried out with appendiceal abscess, complex ovarian tumors, and interrupted ectopic pregnancy in sexually active adolescents.

Treatment of inflammatory diseases of the uterine appendages

In stage 1, conservative therapy is performed. The positive effect of antibacterial therapy within 24-48 hours after the start of treatment serves as the basis for its continuation for 10-14 days. The lack of effect of conservative treatment indicates surgical treatment [2, 3, 7, 11, 13, 14, 20].

The goal of antibacterial therapy is to stop the acute process, prevent its generalization, prevent irreversible morphofunctional changes, and reduce the risk of the acute purulent process becoming chronic.

Methods for optimizing antibacterial therapy in pelvic inflammatory diseases in children: In conclusion, it should be noted that if girls and young women develop symptoms of infectious and inflammatory diseases of the genitals, it is necessary to consult a gynecologist for children and adolescents, since the causes leading to these pathological changes may be different and require a different approach to treatment.

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